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4 The macro-biomolecular mimicry by asbestos
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17 perspective article and literature review
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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

21 This work is dedicated to the memory of Fe Araneta, schoolteacher in Medan
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24

25 ABSTRACT

26 Much is known about specific mechanisms by which asbestos induces mesothelioma (MM).
27 Asbestos causes expression, silencing and mutation in genes, as viewed by methylation and mutation
28 profiles and biomarkers. While much is known about *how* the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) works,
29 the question '*why* does asbestos exert this AOP?' has comparatively not yet been answered with much
30 satisfaction. This paper explores lines of evidence suggesting that asbestos exerts its AOPs because it
31 biophysically resembles various biomechanical macromolecular fibers in the body. This makes the
32 body 'think' that it is operating under a *modus operandi* which it is not. Asbestos fibers resemble
33 endogenous polymeric fibers, which form communication architectures, leading to misrecognition by
34 matrix-sensing systems. The body cannot clear asbestos and applies its reparatory, rebalancing and
35 compensatory *modus operandi* chronically. These otherwise adaptive mechanisms become
36 maladaptive, leading directly to MM. Future research should target asbestos's mimicry to improve
37 detection and reduce chronic damage.

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40 AUTHOR SUMMARY

41 This paper explores why asbestos causes mesothelioma, a deadly cancer. While we understand
42 the cellular mechanisms through which asbestos induces disease, the fundamental reason for this
43 process remains unclear. I propose that asbestos's danger lies in its ability to mimic the body's own
44 essential structural fibers. This mimicry tricks the body into initiating chronic repair and defense
45 responses, which paradoxically lead to damage. The body, unable to clear asbestos, continually
46 activates these pathways, resulting in harmful chronic inflammation and cellular changes that
47 ultimately drive cancer.

48 My work highlights a crucial gap in our understanding: the body's inability to recognize
49 asbestos as a unique threat. Though asbestos is geologically ancient, exposure to high concentrations
50 is relatively new in human evolutionary terms. Consequently, our bodies lack specific mechanisms to
51 effectively neutralize it, and attempts to manage asbestos through existing repair processes become
52 detrimental. Beyond its role as a persistent foreign body, asbestos mimics endogenous fibers,
53 distorting repair signaling. Future research should aim to disrupt this mimicry and enhance the body's
54 ability to resolve or sequester asbestos. By understanding and targeting this mimicry, we can improve
55 detection and reduce the chronic damage caused by asbestos exposure.

56

57 1. INTRODUCTION

58 Asbestos has heat resistant, insulating and strengthening properties, but those properties
59 come at a cost. Asbestos enters the lung by inhalation to cause fibrotic scarring, impaired function,
60 cancer and mortality. Though not the most common, epithelioid mesothelioma (MM) is the signature
61 cancer of asbestos exposure due to its strong etiological specificity. MM manifests after 30-40 years
62 of exposure [1, 2]. Sources of asbestos are its mines, manufacturing and processing plants, steel plants,
63 shipyard and electrical insulation industries. People affected live in areas where asbestos was worked
64 with. Asbestos consumption in the western world peaked in the 80s, where in recent years the peak
65 of mesothelioma cases emerged [3]. Though asbestos use is restricted or banned in industrialized
66 countries, it remains legally used in others, and exposure persists globally through legacy materials
67 and disturbance of soil and rock.

68 The interactions of asbestos with the lungs forms the basis of its pathogenesis. Unraveling the
69 toxic modes of action (TMOAs) by which asbestos prompts MM may involve the concept of molecular
70 mimicry, i.e. how asbestos mimics organic endogenous biofibers. To my knowledge no one has really
71 applied the molecular mimicry concept to asbestos by comparison with biogenic fibers. This is likely
72 because asbestos is not a discrete Ångström-sized soluble signaling molecule or ligand, but rather a
73 micron-sized, inorganic fiber with no evolved clearance mechanism. Based on review literature, I pose
74 that asbestos is a potent carcinogen, due to its likeness to fibrin, collagen, actin, tubulin, chromatin
75 and keratin as well as exogeneous pathogenic biofibers. These fibers perform various tasks as
76 regulators in damage repair, growth, proliferation, colony formation, genetic alteration and immune
77 suppression. The mimicry proposed here refers not to chemical, but to biophysical resemblance at the
78 scale of fiber networks. In the absence of ‘molecular’ similarity, asbestos acts as a structural scaffold
79 that imitates spatial organization of endogenous biopolymeric assemblies — upon which finer
80 molecular interactions are normally orchestrated — enabling aberrant cellular recognition.

81 Asbestos has diameters of <100 nm, with chrysotile asbestos fibers as thin as 30 nm [4];
82 biofibers are of similar diameters [5-7]. The biofibers mentioned play roles in maintaining mesothelial
83 homeostasis. The mesothelium is a single, continuous slippery layer of pavement-like squamous
84 epithelial cells derived from the embryonic mesoderm, is a monolayer of mesothelial cells that blanket
85 the chest wall and lungs. This surface constitutes the interaction with asbestos. Upon introduction *in*
86 *vivo*, asbestos acquires organic coating and negative charge, as have many biofibers [8, 9]. Any Mg and
87 Ca in asbestos, when attacked by lysosomal acid, dissolves, leaving a rigid silica (Si-O) skeleton. The Si-
88 O chemical bond is exceptionally stable, so that ROS and plasmin cannot degrade it further. Indeed,
89 the SiO₂ content and aspect ratio positively correlate with toxicity [10]. The structure of asbestos fibers
90 determines its bio-accessibility and adsorption capacity and, hence, toxicity.

91 Over the years emerged high-throughput next generation sequencing, lower detection limits
92 and new biomarkers. These make it worthwhile to explore the comparison of toxic effects by asbestos
93 in terms of roles of biogenic fibers. In this short review, I explore the concept of macromolecular
94 mimicry by asbestos towards endogenous bodily fibers in terms of biophysics, chemistry and
95 pharmacology. I see similarities between asbestos’ behavior and that of endogenous fibers in the body
96 and conceptualize dose-response based thereon [11-14]. Dose-response curves based on mimicry by
97 asbestos have a mechanistic, rather than purely empirical, rationale. The explored mimicry may sustain
98 unresolved repair and inflammatory signaling, contributing to malignant transformation over time. A
99 conceptual model of this pathological cycle is shown in Fig. 1.

100 This work is a hypothesis-driven perspective that integrates existing toxicological, biophysical,
101 and biomedical literature into a unifying mechanistic framework to explain the persistent pathogenic
102 effects of asbestos exposure.

103 Figure 1. Conceptual model of asbestos mimicry and chronic repair signaling. Asbestos fibers mimic structure and biophysical
104 properties of tissue components, like fibrin and collagen (center), leading to misrecognition by repair and immune systems.
105 This drives a self-reinforcing cycle involving altered signaling, cytoskeletal remodeling, persistent stress and inflammation,
106 and loss of regulatory control — ultimately contributing to mesothelial transformation. The outward spiral illustrates the
107 progression toward malignancy as cellular responses become increasingly dysregulated.
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111 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

112 To describe how biofibers and asbestos are similar, I first outline the roles of endogenous
113 biofibers takes in the body. Describing the mimicry, I follow the known cause effect chains for the
114 development of MM. In the sections below, I introduce asbestos in a physical and chemical sense.
115 Afterwards I will discuss the macromolecular mimicry that asbestos exerts in the body, splitting the
116 sections out per function of biomechanical fiber. Doing so I highlight biomedical findings on asbestos
117 and parallel findings, properties and roles that endogenous fibers have in the body, Fig. 1. I end with
118 an outlook on future research on understanding the disrupting asbestos's biological mimicry to enable
119 targeted therapies that enhance immune recognition and mitigate chronic damage. For explanations
120 of abbreviations I refer to the Table 1 caption.

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123 **Cause-effect pathway:**

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125 ***Introduction of asbestos in vivo***

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127 ***Mechanosensors on cells erroneously register activity & rigidity of fibrin, collagen, actin, etc.***

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129 ***Cells counteracts the perceived overactivity (plasmin, collagenase, matrix remodeling, etc.)***

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131 ***Higher expression of associated genes via e.g., demethylation***

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133 ***DNA demethylation affects ROS levels (ROS catalytically mediates gene expression)***

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135 ***ROS attacks DNA, warranting DNA repair mechanisms (which it also compromises)***

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137 ***Erroneous repair & mutations in genes associated with biofiber activity & matrix remodeling***

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139 ***Onset of mesothelioma***

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142 "To contextualize the hypothesis, we first outline the typical wound healing response, where
143 temporary ECM scaffolds support organized repair and resolution (Figure 2). This physiological
144 balance is disrupted in the presence of persistent exogenous fibers such as asbestos."

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Figure 2. Schematic of endogenous biopolymeric fibers orchestrating wound healing by serving as scaffolds for signaling, metabolic regulation, and matrix remodeling. These coupled processes are normally balanced by stress-response signaling and homeostatic feedback. Asbestos fibers distort this balance by mimicking endogenous biofibers and triggering prolonged or dysregulated repair response. Asbestos causes erroneously perceived overactivity of biofibers, spurring signaling pathways for stress regulation and matrix remodeling. The diagram illustrates how disrupted coordination among remodeling, stress, signaling, and regulatory pathways may lead to loss of control, mutation accumulation, and eventual carcinogenesis. Main agents binding endogenous human biofibers *in vivo* (bold), and closely associated metabolic partners (non-bold). The higher the mismatch between stress (right) and matrix remodeling (left), the more their autoregulation (up) is disturbed. Upon such mismatch, the body 'tries' to get out of a repair cycle for disturbed steady state, while mutations continue to accumulate. Imagine the levels of biofibers (collagen, fibrin, elastin, etc.) at the top as a central hub connecting all domains, with regulatory and signaling pathways radiating outward.

158 **2.1. Fibrin dynamics, hemostasis and hypoxia**

159 A healthy body needs balance between blood flow and its congestion [15]. Regulated by
160 immune cells [16], a matrix of fibrin and platelets modulates proliferation of cells therein for healing
161 and vascularization. In serous cavities, mesothelial cells [1] regulate levels of fibrin. Reaction between
162 fibrinogen monomers and the converse (lysis), constantly takes place [17]. Oligofibrin coagulates and
163 hydrophobically crosslink to a large mesh [18]. Conversely, plasmin breaks down fibrin clots into
164 fibrinogen [19, 20]. Plasmin, thrombin, calcium, pH, factor XIII and ionic strength all influence mesh
165 strength and geometry [21, 22]. Asbestos appears as fibrous bundles or networks resembled by a mesh
166 of fibrin, while airborne asbestos are individual fibers that mimic individual fibrin filaments. Structural
167 resemblance at both the mesh- and single-fiber level may contribute to biological misrecognition. The
168 rigidity of asbestos is as if fibrin with much antiplasmin, calcium or glucose is present. Asbestos thus
169 interferes with fibrin's role in damage repair. Like fibrin, asbestos affects blood clotting [23] e.g. by
170 inducing TF [24] and the urokinase-type plasminogen activator [25]. Fibrin aids cell differentiation to
171 platelet-producing megakaryocytes [26]. Similarly, asbestos provides an adhesion matrix and induces
172 MPF. Asbestos is more potent than is fibrin: as view from half-lives: of fibrin is ~3 days, vs asbestos
173 ~3000 days (~10 years). Extracellular matrices generate signals to regulate cell shape, differentiation,
174 survival, migration and proliferation. Both fibrinogen and asbestos interact with Hh signaling [27] and
175 integrins (receptor glycoproteins) to mediate adhesion, aggregation and clot retraction [28].

176 Oxygen is a rheostat, reflecting the balance between coagulation and fibrinolysis. Low O₂
177 stimulates fibrinolytic activity [29]. Conversely, high levels of fibrinogen monomers stimulate
178 mesothelial cells to promote cell growth and angiogenesis [30-32], increasing O₂. High O₂ causes intra-
179 alveolar fibrin deposition [33] and promotes cross-linking of fibrin oligomers [34], impairing gas
180 exchange. Partial pressure of O₂ is tied to pCO₂ and, hence, pH. Acidity is generated by tumor cells due
181 to lactic acid production. Indeed, pH 7.3 sees lower mesothelial plasminogen activator production (PAI-
182 1) than does pH 5.2 [35, 36]. An acidic microenvironment, linked to cellular respiration, is a potential
183 niche for a tumor [37]. Hypoxia stimulates EV secretion, via increased ROS production by the
184 mitochondrial electron transport chain and HIF-1 [38]. Asbestos erroneously make the body 'think'
185 that metabolism is actively lowering O₂ levels by operating under e.g. high thrombin and fibrinogen.
186 'Mistaking' asbestos for fibrin, the body compensates (to degrade) by producing plasmin (activators)
187 and urokinase. This is an overcompensation, causing 'too much repair'. As balance is needed, too much
188 repair is damaging.

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190 **2.2. Messaging, growth and clotting**

191 While fibrin regulates cell proliferation, it cannot do so without platelets. Asbestos may mimic
192 features of fibrin and collagen, key platelet modulators. By presenting rigid, charged, and fiber-like
193 surfaces, asbestos would influence platelet adhesion and activation, disrupting localized hemostatic
194 balance. Indeed, adverse blood clotting is a major side effect of mesothelioma [39]. Platelet plugging
195 and coagulation each induce the other to form crosslinks to ensure structural soundness of clots [21,
196 40, 41]. Both fibrin and asbestos induce expression of TF, which binds to factor VII, to increase
197 production of platelet activator thrombin [42, 43]. Cancer cells use a platelet-filled fibrin thrombus as
198 a 'cloak' to escape immune T-cell surveillance via 'programmed cell death' signals [44, 45]. Platelet-
199 derived EVs are the most abundant EV: >75% of EVs derive from platelets, split-off fragments of
200 cytoplasm from lung megakaryocytes [46, 47]. As fibrin binds integrin on platelet-derived EVs, levels
201 of fibrinogen correlate with integrin and tetraspanins [48-51]. Asbestos stimulates growth induced by
202 platelet EVs [20, 52]: macrophages exposed to asbestos express tetraspanins to generate 'ferroptotic
203 EVs', which transport Fe (ferritin) into mesothelial cells causing them to become mitotic [52]. This
204 appears to be a subset, as indeed, platelets aggregate to the endothelium turn on receptors and
205 secrete messengers like VEGF, promoting mesenchymal differentiation, proliferation and angiogenesis
206 [44, 45, 53].

207 Complex sorting mechanisms select EV cargo [54] to signal cell maintenance, differentiation,
208 tissue repair and regeneration [55]. Asbestos alters protein loads in EVs, altering mesothelial gene
209 expression, like epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition [56]. Mesothelial cells can secrete TGF- β ,
210 fibroblast growth factors, and platelet-derived growth factors [57], like the polypeptide cytokine MPF,
211 which stimulates colony-forming activity and regulates platelet production and function [58-60]. While
212 MPF is a marker of mesothelioma [61, 62], interleukins also have megakaryocyte potentiating activity
213 [63]. EVs may contain DNA/RNA, receptors, cytokines, metabolites, metals (transferrin), regulating
214 adhesion, migration, contraction, cell growth, proliferation or angiogenesis [55, 64]. Mesotheliomal
215 EVs contain mesothelin, EGFR, fibulin, platelet-derived growth factor receptor β , ras-related proteins,
216 TNF receptors, macrophage colony-stimulating factors, and DNA damage-binding proteins, growth
217 factors, tetraspanins, LAMP-1 and immune cell killing factors [65, 66]. The more of such oncogenic EVs,
218 the more cancer cells will be the result, and *vice versa*.

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224 **2.3. Cytoskeleton, surface activation and shaping**

225 Asbestos also shares features—such as linearity, stiffness, aspect ratio—with actin and tubulin
226 filaments. This may contribute to misinterpretation of asbestos as an intracellular biopolymer scaffold.
227 Such mimicry may involve physical cues like shape, charge, and rigidity—that guide cell sensing and
228 organization. Indeed, cell responses to stress involves organization of actin/tubulin. Mesothelial cells
229 produce the adhesion glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI) anchor protein, mesothelin [67]. Mesothelin
230 binds to mucin-16 (CA125) which links to the actin cytoskeleton [68] to aid cell adhesion. In MM,
231 mutated and metastasized mesothelial cells have mesothelin overexpression on membrane cilia [69,
232 70] which are abnormally long and branching, with disfunctioning mesothelin-mucin interaction [71-
233 73]. Integrins mediate adhesion-dependent cell death [74], but MM cells are resistant to cell death.
234 Mesothelin enables cell survival by suppressing Bim induction via extracellular signal-regulated kinase
235 signaling [75]. The NF2 gene encodes a cytoskeletal radixin-like protein, a cilia-forming protein and
236 regulator of TKs for proliferation, survival, invasiveness and migration, integrin signaling [76, 77]. The
237 actin cytoskeleton regulates mesothelial shape and permeability [78, 79]. Other adhesion-related gene
238 expression CTHRC1, fibrillin, platelet-derived GFs, PDLIM3 and neurotrimin are altered [80].
239 Tetraspanins trigger platelet activation and modulate cell adhesion and migration [81]. Surface
240 activation of platelets involves reorganization of stress fiber-like structures [82];

241 Asbestos may mimic persistent stress signals and (hence) distort stress-response, leading cells
242 to misinterpret the tissue environment and sustain pathological responses. A pathway through which
243 misinterpretation may occur involves the cytoskeleton, mechanosensing, and cilia. Asbestos interacts
244 and interferes with cytoskeletal systems and ‘ciliary integrity’ through stress signaling [83].
245 Mesothelium cells have protruding cilia, finger-like membrane protrusions; centrioles of ~25nm thick
246 microtubules, bound to the membrane via palmitoylation and linker proteins, supported by the
247 cytoskeleton [84, 85]. Cilia transduce signals to intracellular compartments via the Hh pathway [86]. As
248 cilia increase the surface area, more absorption takes place as slipperiness is lost [57]. Hh is normally
249 inactivated; patched (Ptc), a transmembrane tumor suppressor keeps the Hh pathway off by inhibiting
250 Smo. Hh ligands stimulate actin stress fibers, altering cell stiffness [87, 88]. MM involves altered EMT
251 [89, 90], stiffness and adhesion [91, 92]. Loss of adhesion promotes tumor cell invasion [93]. Hh
252 signaling can induce EMT as SMO/GPCR carries Hh signals across the membrane. In MM, non-
253 functioning cilia-related oncoprotein SMO and tf GLI1 are expressed [86, 94-97]. Asbestos disrupts the
254 cytoskeleton, inducing abnormal actin polymerization [98-100]. As a rigid surface, asbestos may distort
255 cellular stiffness sensing and promote a (rebalancing) shift toward a softer, more invasive phenotype
256 — consistent with known responses to matrix stiffening [101]. Indeed, tubulin acetylation increases
257 cytoskeletal stiffness, and enhances resistance to chemotherapy [102]. Keratin is a diagnostic
258 biomarker for MM [103]. Vimentin too, normally low in mesothelial cells, is a marker for MM,
259 indicating altered cytoskeleton [103-105].

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264 **2.4. Immune detection and phagocytosis**

265 The body may 'think' asbestos is a fiber from a biopathogen to be destroyed. Though
266 extracellular receptors for certain biopathogens are composed of actin [106], which asbestos
267 interferes with. As the amount of biomechanical fibers needs to be balanced, foreign fibers needs to
268 be eliminated. Upon too many fibers, the body senses a higher potential for phagocytosis.
269 Phagocytosis requires actin-polymerization, induction of receptors and internalization of plasma
270 membrane. Fibers from fungal spores may cause mesothelioma [107]. Spores, bacterial filaments and
271 fibrin, 'normally' cleared by the body via phagocytosis, are relatively flexible or can be made flexible.
272 By contrast, asbestos fibers are rigid. Hh signaling acts as a macrophage attractant via a Smo-
273 dependent mechanism [108].

274 Both asbestos and fibrin affect actin polymerization and trigger inflammatory release and TNF-
275 α receptors on mesothelial cells [99, 109, 110]. TNF- α activates NF- κ B leading to cell survival, increasing
276 the percent of mesothelial cells that survives asbestos exposure, increasing the cell pool susceptible
277 to malignant transformation [110]. TNF- α also promotes insulin resistance; glucose stimulates invasion
278 by cancer cells via AMPK/mTOR/S6 and MAPK [111]. Cancer cells require glucose, which in turn drives
279 thrombin and plasminogen activity [35]. Both fibrin- and asbestos-activated macrophages release
280 mitogens and growth factors to proliferate mesothelial cells [112, 113]. Macrophages enable
281 phagocytosis, fibrosis, repair, etc. As CRP binds fibrin and TNF α regulates macrophage function,
282 phagocytosis is related to both CRP and TNF- α , Figure 3B;C. Fig. 2 summarizes homeostatic
283 coordination of stress responses, inflammation, ECM remodeling, and regulation triggered by
284 biopolymeric fibers. While not depicting asbestos directly, it provides conceptual grounding for how
285 these processes are perturbed by asbestos mimicry.

286 Cell lines have different phagocytic capacities: RAW macrophages, but not 937 macrophages,
287 can internalize asbestos fibers of >15 μ m. Mesothelial cells can differentiate to display phagocytosis of
288 both fibrin and asbestos, via vitronectin, integrin and annexin [114-117]. While not technically
289 classified as an integrin, mesothelin regulates phagocytosis [118]. Macrophages secrete interleukins
290 to cause CRP to rise. CRP binds asbestos, fibrin, tumor phospholipids [119] and a panoply of microbial
291 antigens, including fungi, yeasts, bacteria, and parasites, to stimulate phagocytosis and lysosome
292 activation [120-123]. In the case of asbestos, though, U937-phagosomes neither recruited the
293 lysosome marker LAMP-1, nor fused with lysosomes [123]. Meaning phagocytosis fails.

294 Figure 3. Molecular binding ratios of fibrinogen and related proteins is critical to predict how they influence tumor growth
295 [28, 113, 124-126]. A: The more tumor cells, the more mesothelin, data adapted from published sources [127-129]. B:
296 Phagocytic marker CRP versus fibrinogen, data adapted from [130-133]. C: CRP versus tumor size, data adapted from
297 published sources [134, 135].
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302 **2.5. Balancing reactive oxygen and nitrogen species**

303 Intact tissues perfused with O₂ creates potential for generation of ROS. Asbestos-induced ROS
304 imbalance drives mesothelioma [136]. The presence of (biogenic) fibers interrelates with the presence
305 of ROS, each moderating the other. ROS partake in cell signaling [137], breaking down and
306 phagocytosing fibrin [138], which acts as an antioxidant [139] as it has ROS-active groups. ROS signals
307 are mediated to target proteins by carbonyl compounds like glycolaldehyde, [140] which result in
308 fibrinogen and protein aggregation, suppressing fibrinogenesis [141]. ROS oxidize phospholipids,
309 signaling stress. Glioblastoma cells lacking CDKN2A show increased lipid peroxidation [142]. CRP binds
310 oxidized phospholipids, enhancing phagocytosis [143]. Macrophages use oxidized phospholipids as
311 inflammatory signals, regulating neutrophil ROS production [144-146]. Unlike fibrin which has
312 antioxidant properties, asbestos is prooxidant [147]. The body registers asbestos as elevating ROS,
313 whereas fibrin would have lowered ROS. Mistaking it for fibrin, the body 'tries' to compensate by
314 producing prooxidants, which in fact exacerbate the prooxidant properties of asbestos.

315 Aberrant tyrosine nitration (TN) of proteins is associated with MM [148], as TN controls
316 proliferation, differentiation, survival and mitosis. TN is mediated by RNS like ONOO⁻, •NO₂ and •NO.
317 TN involves oxidizing tyrosine to a tyrosyl radical and diffusion-controlled reaction with •NO₂ to yield
318 3-nitrotyrosine [149]. Tissues perfused with O₂ produce •NO, which inhibits platelet activation.
319 Conversely, lowering O₂ via vasoconstriction involves tyrosine nitration and activation of ERK1/2 [150].
320 Asbestos, like fibrin, scavenges nitric oxide (•NO), reducing its concentration and nitrosation [151,
321 152]. While asbestos modifies tyrosines via -NO₂ adducts, it also increases NOS expression as a
322 compensatory response [151, 153]. Asbestos mimics tyrosine phosphorylation (TP), activating kinases
323 [154, 155], and shifts cell growth from inhibitory (p53) to proliferative (HIF-1α) by lowering •NO [156,
324 157]. Additionally, asbestos enhances 8-OHdG formation in DNA by altering the NO₂⁻/NO balance
325 [151]. Binding of antitumor mesothelin antibodies on cancerous cell membranes, cause lactate
326 depletion, affecting ROS level [158].

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329 **2.6. Iron biocatalysis and homeostasis**

330 As iron interconverts between Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺, it mediates ROS/RNS. Lysosomes exploit this by
331 sequestering Fe, which are a source of ROS, acid and enzymes [159, 160]. Therewith, lysosomes
332 attempt to digest asbestos [161], which fails (“frustrated phagocytosis”) [99], leaving ‘asbestos bodies’
333 with redox activated Fe-rich proteins behind [162]. Such coating ‘normally’ occurs when Fe from
334 digested hemoproteins is stored in phagocytes as ferritin and insoluble aggregates of hemosiderin
335 [163, 164]. As such, asbestos is a sink for iron, disrupting iron homeostasis [165]. Coated asbestos is
336 rich in Fe³⁺, which induces ROS [112, 166-168]. For biomaterials, ROS would eventually result in
337 degradation. Degradation of asbestos, though, takes decades, all the while mediating mutagenicity
338 [169]. Indeed, Fe aids NO₂⁻ and 8-OHdG formation by asbestos [151]. In response to ROS, antioxidants
339 and Fe chelators, glutathione peroxidase and oxidoreductase inhibit ferroptotic cell death, the Fe-
340 dependent peroxidation (inactivation) of membrane lipids [170]. Again, parallels between fibrin and
341 asbestos exist: as fibrinogen binds ferritin, increase in Fe affects fibrin deposition and [171-173]
342 coagulation kinetics [174, 175]. Excess free Fe in blood can generate insoluble fibrin-like material [176].

343 While Fe chelators attenuate inflammation [177], excess Fe chelators and antioxidant capacity
344 (heme-iron) speed up carcinogenesis [178]. In cytosol, asbestos are coated with Fe complexes but
345 chelators can remobilize Fe [179]. MM cells express mesoderm-specific transcription factors for
346 differentiation and show active Fe uptake. Indeed, tumors require Fe to grow and divide. In mice fed
347 26 times more Fe, tumor growth was 112% per week (vs. 62% in control) [180, 181], consistent with a
348 correlation between Fe content and tumor volume (Figure 4A). This relationship could mean that Fe
349 dysregulation — such as that triggered by asbestos — may contribute to tumorigenesis via both ROS
350 and the promotion of proliferative environments. Levels of hepcidin correlate with cancer progression
351 [180, 182]. Growth and differentiation factors promotes synthesis of hepcidin which reduces release
352 of Fe from macrophage ferritin storages [180]. Iron signaling, ROS/RNS, and ferroptosis are linked to
353 carcinogenesis. While ferroptosis, an iron-dependent cell death, can curb tumor growth, iron chelators
354 inhibit it. Conversely, glutathione peroxidase inhibition or glutathione depletion induces ferroptosis.
355 Within the tumor microenvironment, myeloid-derived suppressor cells and cancer-associated
356 fibroblasts modulate immune suppression and ferroptosis, respectively [183].

357
358 Figure 4. The influence of ROS/RNS and Fe on methylation patterns and collagen production, marks cancer evolution by
359 altering tissue structure and gene expression.

360 A: Correlation between serum tumor volume (y-axis) and ferritin (green), iron in tumor µg/g (blue, red), data adapted from
361 published sources [184].

362 B: Mean tumor diameter versus methylation activity (as measured via (nor)metaphrine, nmol/L), data from published
363 sources [185, 186]. The relationship matches DNA methylation versus lifetime cancer risk [187].

364 C: Tumor weight versus collagen content as measured via hydroxyproline by HPLC, data dapted with permission from
365 [188].

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368 **2.7. Epigenetics and mitosis**

369 Generally, biotic stress causes dynamic DNA and histone methylation [189, 190]. DNA
370 methylation, which influences gene expression and cell differentiation, links to coagulome gene
371 expression [191] and fibrinogen mRNA levels [192]. Histone methylation also modifies chromatin
372 structure, impacting its dynamics and accessibility for transcription [193-195]. In MM, methylation
373 occurs in mesothelial CpG sites and genes for transcriptional regulators (e.g. MIR21, SPEN) [196]. In
374 white blood cells, genes regulating transcription and stress response show distinct methylation
375 affecting immune response [197, 198]. Cellular stress can drive chromatin flexibility via demethylation.
376 However, rigid intracellular asbestos may trigger a counteractive demethylation response, as the cell
377 attempts to restore normal chromatin dynamics. Neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs), composed of
378 DNA and granule proteins, trap pathogens and trigger coagulation [199]. While most chromatin is
379 nuclear, it condenses during mitosis. Asbestos fibers mimic mitotic chromatin, potentially disrupting
380 mitosis [98]. Mesothelial damage induces mitosis and cellular transformation [57, 200], but asbestos
381 interference with tubulin, a key component of mitotic spindles, may impair this process.

382 DNA methyltransferase (DMT) methylates cytosine via a nucleophilic attack of the C-5 atom
383 on the methyl group of S-adenosyl methionine [201]. ROS-altered methylation drives malignant
384 transformation [202]. Superoxide can also catalyze this methylation [201]. Nitric oxide (NO) modulates
385 methylation by affecting demethylases and iron availability [203, 204]. Metanephrine and
386 normetanephrine, demethylation products, serve as biomarkers for malignant mesothelioma (MM),
387 Fig. x. Asbestos exposure is linked to hypomethylation, notably the loss of MSLN methylation in tumors
388 [205]. Hypomethylation in malignant mesothelioma (MM) concerns genes like RARB, GPCRs,
389 peroxidases [206] [207, 208], as well as zinc finger tfs and HOOK2 in blood cells [167]. In lung cancer,
390 hypomethylation of the DDR1 gene promotes EMT [209, 210]. Conversely, hypermethylation, which
391 silences tumor suppressor genes and tfs, is also observed in MM [208] [211] and lung cancer [210].
392 METTL3-mediated methylation, however, promotes tumor progression via sHh signaling [212].
393 Mesothelial damage associated- and DNA binding proteins drive the onset of MM [213]. BAP1 loss in
394 MM disrupts DNA repair, contributing to increased genomic instability.

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398 **2.8. Basement membrane dynamics and remodeling**

399 The basement membrane (BM), composed of collagens, fibronectin, and other proteins,
400 connects mesothelium and endothelium, providing tissue support and signaling [57, 214]. Collagen and
401 fibronectin interactions contribute to tumor progression [215]. Fibroblasts, and transformed
402 mesothelial cells, produce collagen, driving EMT in the tumor microenvironment [1, 90]. Tumor cell
403 migration involves metalloenzymes like collagenases, which degrade the basement membrane (BM)
404 and facilitate invasion [92, 216, 217]. Collagen degradation allows tumor cells to traverse the BM and
405 cleave E-cadherin, promoting EMT [92]. Collagen type IV can be modified by nitrite, affecting adjacent
406 cells [218]. Collagen-bound DDR1/2 act as mechanosensors for stiffness, shear and tension, regulating
407 MMP production and EMT [219-221]. DDR1 is implicated in tumor promotion and immunotherapy
408 resistance [222, 223].

409 MSLN expression modulates omental fibril organization and collagen/elastin density [71]
410 [224]. MSLN deletion disrupts mesothelial architecture and collagen organization, while MSLN
411 influences TGF β 1-mediated fibrogenesis [71]. Notably, low MSLN tumors exhibit higher collagen
412 density and increased abundance of MUC16, the mucin binding partner of MSLN [225]. Type IV
413 collagen promotes tumor cell proliferation and migration [226]. Tumor-specific 'collagen signatures'
414 include unorganized distant fibrils and aligned edge fibrils, with radial orientation at invasion sites
415 [227]. High collagen density upregulates regulatory T cell markers and induces a stiff, collagen-rich
416 tumor microenvironment [228]. Despite structural similarities, asbestos differs from collagen matrices.
417 The body's attempt to 'soften' the perceived rigidity of asbestos leads to elastin production and
418 activation of matrix-remodeling genes [229, 230]. Asbestos induces autoantibodies that alter MMP
419 expression, promoting collagen deposition [231]. Asbestos also decreases DDR2 expression while
420 inducing various MMPs and their inhibitors, TIMP-1/2 [232, 233]. DDR1 expression correlates with
421 tumor purity and inversely with T cell infiltration [234].

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426 TABLE 1. Summary of receptors, hormones and genes regulating biofiber activity, coupled to evidence from literature on the
 427 compensatory mechanistic thereon by asbestos via induction, transcription, methylation, etc. Mutations relevant to the
 428 asbestos-mimicking pathways are also given. All pathways are related to each other via complex feedback loops, simplified.
 429 This table is intended as an integrative map linking biofiber functions, regulatory pathways, and asbestos-induced
 430 perturbations, rather than as an exhaustive or linear pathway representation.

Function time and space (why of where and when) biofibers occur	Biofiber – Matrix and adhesion remodelers that bind biofibers	Major down- and upstream signaling agents to the binders, regulating their activity and expression	Mechanistic inferences from studies on asbestos or related mimicking effects impacting regulatory pathways	Primary mutations relevant to the pathway
Coagulation in ECM and bloodstream	Fibrin – Plasmin <i>PLG</i>	Urokinase ←(stimulate) growth factors* ↓ (converts plasminogen) Plasmin → (degrades) fibrin	[57, 235, 236]	FGFR3 [237]
Platelet modulation in bloodstream and on platelet surfaces	Fibrin – Thrombin <i>F2</i>	TF + Factor VIIa ↓ Factor Xa → Thrombin → Fibrin ↑ (Amplification) Thrombin → Factor V/VIII	[238]	K-ras/TF [239]
Platelet modulation at ECM and clot site	Fibrin – Factor XIII <i>F13A1/ F13B</i>	Thrombin ↓ (Activates) Factor XIII(a) ← (phosphorylates) TKs ↓ (Crosslinks) Fibrin + Fibronectin ← (phosphorylates) TKs	[240]	ABL1, RET [237] Tyrosine kinase
Platelet modulation at clot site and platelet surfaces	Fibrin – Integrin α-IIb β3 <i>ITGA2B/ ITGB3</i>	Integrin αIIbβ3 ←(increase) MPF (<i>MSLN</i> , partner) ← MUC16 ← Hyaluronan ↓ (binds fibrin) Fibrin -platelet clots ↓ (Signaling) SrcK, MAPK/ERK,PI3K/AKT/PTEN → (regulate)clotting	[241]	PIK3CA [237]
Cellular respiration in endothelial cells and bloodstream	Fibrin – VEGF-A <i>VEGFA</i>	HIF-1→ VEGFA →VEGFR→SrcKinases→MAPK/ERK,PI3K/AKT ↓ (Endothelial Activation) (e)NOS → NO → platelet deactivation → reduced fibrin formation	[242, 243]	EGFR, PIK3CA [237]
Coagulation in ECM and local tissue	Fibrin – PAI-1 <i>SERPINE1</i>	PAI-1 Expression ←(Stimulates) TGF-β ↓ (inhibits) Plasmin(ogen) activity ↓ (Reduces fibrinolysis) Increased fibrin ← (increases) thrombin	[244]	SMAD4 [237]
Remodeling of ECM, and local tissue	Fibrin, collagen – Fibulin-1 <i>FBLN1</i>	neutrophil ROS→lipid peroxidation←(counters)GPX4&FSP1 ↓ (generates carbonyl compounds, modifies) ECM fibronectin, fibrin , elastin, collagen ↓ (influences) Fibulin-1 & cathepsin B → degrade ECM ↓ (activates) CDKN2A,ERK1/2→cell aging, ECM Remodel.	[65, 245-248]	Inactivating deletion of CDKN2A/2B/ARF TSGs [165, 249, 250]
Actin remodeling in cell membrane and cytoplasm	Actin – Actin-Related Proteins (ARPs) <i>ARPC</i>	RAS / Hippo (LATS1/2, MST1/2) ↓ (via YAP/TAZ) Rho GTPases, kinases ↓ (Activate) WASP/N-WASP, Scar ↓ (Activates) ARP2/3 complex → (Branching) Actin	[251]	RAS [252] Hippo (LATS1/2, MST1/2) FBXW7, RET [237]
Actin elongation in cytoplasm, cell cortex	Actin – Formins <i>ACTR</i>	RAS / Hippo (LATS1/2, MST1/2) ↓ (via YAP/TAZ) Rho GTPases, kinases ↓ (Activate) ACTR (formins) ↓ (nucleates, elongates) Actin filaments	[251, 253]	RAS [252] Hippo (LATS1/2, MST1/2) FBXW7, RET [237]
Actin stabilization in cytoplasm	Actin – Actin-associated LIM protein <i>PDLIM3</i>	Rho GTPases, kinases ↓ (Activate) PDLIM3 → (Binds) Actin Filaments	[80, 253, 254]	PDLIM3 [255]
Signaling at adhesions sites, interface between cell and ECM	Actin – α-actinin <i>ACTN1</i> ,	Talin and/or Vinculin ← (activate) Integrins ↓ (Talin binds actin filaments, Vinculin recruits) α-actinin ← (Phosphorylate) kinases	[256]	A combination ?

	Vinculin, Talin	↓ (Strengthens connections, influences) ECM/ Actin cytoskeleton→(m.)NF-κB/FAK/Src signal ↓Expression (ZF, bHLH tfs & nucl. receptors)		
Actin-myosin contraction in cytoplasm	Actin – Myosin (I,II,V,VI) <i>MYO/MYH</i>	ERK1/2 Signaling ↓ (Phosphorylates & Activates) Myosin ↓ (Binds, moves) Actin Filaments ↓ (influences via membrane/cilia-associated proteins) Membrane & cilia function ← (regulate) calmodulin/Ca ²⁺	[248, 257]	A combination ?
Cytoskeletal organization, intersections in cytoplasm	Actin, cytoskeletal tubulin – Radixin-like, cilia-forming Merlin (ERMs) <i>NF2</i>	Merlin ↓ (Binds) Actin Filaments & Microtubule-Associated Proteins ↓ (Regulates)	[258]	Inactivating TSG NF2 [249, 250, 259, 260] . Loss of Merlin [258] Radixin/RDX [259, 260]
Cytoskeletal modulation in cytoplasm, at cell surface	Actin cytoskeleton – Mesothelin <i>MSLN</i>	Actin & Tubulin Organization ↓ (Influences) CA125 → (Modulates)Cytoskeleton&Cell-MatrixInteraction		Region (296–359) of MSLN (CA125 binding site) [261]
Hedgehog-cytoskeleton control, throughout the cell	Actin, cytoskeletal tubulin – β-arrestin <i>ARRB</i>	SMO inhibited by GLI2/PTCH1 ← METTL3 Methylation ↓ (Hedgehog (SHH) binding & Phosphorylation) GPCR/GPR135/SMO Activation, GLI1 modulation ↓ (Transduction & Transcription) Zinc Finger Protein GLI1 activation & Hh Expression ↓ (β-arrestin Binds Phosphorylated SMO) Actin/Tubulin Cytoskeleton Dynamics	[86, 95-97]	ptc, smo and sufu that activate Hh [237, 262, 263]
Microtubule stability, apoptotic regulation in cytoplasm	Tubulin, cytoskeletal – Bim <i>BCL2L11</i>	Bim Expression ← stress (FOXO, p53 tfs) ↓ (Binds to Microtubules, Dynein LC8) Microtubule Stability ↓ (Apoptotic Stimuli, Kinase Phosphorylation) Bim Release&Bcl-2 Inhibition → Microtubule instability	[75, 264]	p53 [265] FBXW7 [237]
Cell-cell anchoring junctions at membranes	Keratin – Plakoglobin, Plakophilin, Desmoplakin	Desmosome cadherins(<i>CDH15</i>)←(influences)Wnt & MAPK ↓ (Binds) Plakoglobin/Plakophilin,Desmoplakin ←(infl.)Wnt&MAPK ↓ (Anchors, Regulates) Keratin Filaments → (modulate) cell adhesion, tissue integrity	[104, 266]	APC (wnt signaling) [237]
Cytoplasm, cytoskeletal crosslinking with the ECM	Tubulin, Vimentin, actin – Plectin <i>PLEC</i>	Plectin ←(Binds ECM) integrin β4 ↓ (Crosslinks) Vimentin, actin, tubulin → (regulates) cytoskeleton	[103, 257]	A combination ?
Along microtubules, tubule transport in cytoplasm	Tubulin – HOOK2	HOOK2 → (microtubule-based organelle transport) ↓ (Binds, regulates) tubulin → (regulates) cytoskeleton organization	[211]	A combination ?
Spindle regulation in cytoplasm during cell division	Tubulin – Microtubule-Ass. Proteins <i>MAP, KMN</i>	MAPs → (Bind & Regulate) Tubulin spindles ↓ (Interacts With Kinetochores) KMN → (senses attachment, Activates SAC) ↓ SAC (Mad, Bub) → (Regulates) Cell Cycle Progression	[267]	A combination ?
Chromatin regulation in cell nucleus	Chromatin – HMGB1, Histones <i>HIST1, ASXL1/2</i>	Histones ↓(H3K27methyl-,acetyltransfer,demethyl/acetylase) HMGB1 Binding & Chromatin Remodeling ↓ Chromatin accessibility →(influences) gene expression	[213, 268]	MTAP frequently codeleted with CDKN2A [250, 258, 269]
Gene regulation in cell nucleus	Chromatin – NF-κB, Zinc Finger, bHLH, KLF11, HIF-1 <i>NFKB/REL, ZNF, MYC, ASCL</i>	Cell stimuli (cytokines, stress) ↓ (activation) tfs (NF-κB/REL, MYC, ASCL, KLF11, p53, HIF-1) ↓ (binding to) Chromatin DNA ↓ (activators/repressors, remodeling complexes) Histone changes, DNA accessibility → gene expression	[270]	p53 [265]
Gene expression in cell nucleus	Chromatin – RARβ	RARB ← (binds) retinoic acid ↓ (binds) RAREs on chromatin ↓ (recruit chromatin methyltransferases and modulators, then change) Chromatin accessibility/structure → gene expression	[207, 208]	A combination ?

DNA/chromatin remodeling in cell nucleus	Chromatin – DNA Repair Proteins (BRCA1 Ass. Protein 1), SWI/SNF XP(A,B,C,P), BAP1	DNA Damage ↓ (repair Proteins BAP1, SWI/SNF XP(A,B,C,P)) BAP1 → deubiquitination & chromatin histone changes SWI/SNF XP → chromatin nucleotide excision repair ↓ (chromatin accessible; excision/strand break repair) DNA Integrity & cell cycle regulation	[242, 258]	Inactivating alterations in BAP1 DNA repair and TSGs [249, 250, 258-260, 271, 272]
Immune response in intercellular space, blood, etc.	Pilin – Antibodies IgG, IgM, and IgA, IgE? <i>IGHG, IGHM, IGHA, IGHE?</i>	Bacterial pilin ↓ Immune recognition (PRRs, B cells) AMPs (defensins, cathelicidins) & Antibodies IgG, IgM, and IgA produced ↓ Bind pilin Neutralization, enhanced phagocytosis	[273]	p53 [265, 274]
Immune response and phagocytosis at intercellular space and surface	Chitin – Chitinase (-like proteins) Pentraxins	Chitin (e.g. fungal) ↓ binding Pentraxin ↓ Activation of Immune Signaling Phagocytosis/endocytosis of chitin-containing organisms ↓ Lysosome fusion LAMP-1 → chitinase activity	[275, 276]	p53 [265]
Immune response and phagocytosis at (inter)cellular space and surface	Chitin – (C-type) lectins <i>CLEC/MBL/ CD209, CRP</i>	Fungal Chitin ↓ Immune Recogn, PRRs: C-type lectins , CLEC/MBL/CD209, CRP ↓ (opsonization, activation) Immune cells, macrophages → phagocytosis	[277]	p53 [265]
Phagocytosis, macrophage surface and cytoplasm	Chitin – Integrins, e.g. α M β 2 <i>ITGAM/ CD18</i>	Fungal chitin ↓ (binding to) Macrophage Integrin αMβ2 ↓ Integrin activation, signaling pathways Phagocytosis → lysosomal degradation of chitin	[278]	p53 [265]
Immune response, IL-6 signaling in intercellular space and ECM	Chitin, collagen, fibrin – Fibronectin <i>FN1</i> , vitronectin <i>VTN</i>	Chitin/collagen/fibrin ← (bind) fibronectin & vitronectin ↓ Tyrosine Kinase Activation Tyrosine Phosphorylation & IL-6 Release ↓ IL-6R Signals (JAK/STAT) → modulated fiber processing	[215, 221]	p53 [265] RAS [252]
BM functioning, remodeling at ECM/cell interface	Collagen – Integrins α 1 β 1, α 2 β 1, α 11 β 1 <i>ITGA/ITGB1, ITGA11/ ITGB1</i>	Collagen → Integrin Activation (tetraspanin-modulated) ↓ MXRA5 & GLT25D2 Activity (tetraspanin-modulated) ↓ Collagen remodeling & degradation	[260]	MXRA5 [259, 260] RET [237]
BM functioning, remodeling, at ECM/cell interface	Collagen – Laminin <i>LAMA/LAMB/ LAMC</i>	Laminin ↓ (binding collagen) Collagen-laminin Complexes ↓ binding to integrins Integrins activate → (KRAS/RRAS) signals by MAPK, PI3K/Akt	[279]	PIK3Ca, RET [237]
BM functioning, remodeling, at ECM/cell interface	Collagen – Collagen triple helix repeat containing 1 <i>CTHRC1</i>	Extracellular collagen Fibrils ↓ (bind to CTHRC1) Modulation of collagen fibrillogenesis & remodeling ↓ (activate) Integrin, KRAS/RRAS2 → signaling by MAPK, PI3K/Akt	[80]	PIK3CA, RET [237]
BM functioning, remodeling, at ECM/cell interface	Collagen – collagenases (<i>MT-MMP</i>)	Collagen ↓ (activation by DDR1/2, tyrosine phosphorylation) MMP binding & collagen degradation (modulated by: tetraspanins, K-Ras/R-Ras2, ERK1/2, Cathepsin B, CSF1)	[231, 232]	A combination ?
BM functioning, remodeling, transcription throughout the cell	Collagen – discoidin domain receptors DDR1/2	Collagen ↓ Binding to DDR1/DDR2 DDR1/DDR2 activation & Tyrosine Phosphorylation ↓ K-Ras/R-Ras2 & ERK1/2 Activation WNT Signaling ↓ Angiotensin II, TGF- β /BMP2/GDF-15 Signaling ↓ Dlx5/Hand1 activation (gene transcription) Collagen Synthesis	[209, 280]	APC (wnt signaling), SMAD4, RET [237]
BM functioning, remodeling at ECM/cell interface	Collagen – Annexin	Extracellular collagen ↓ (binding to) Annexin & cell membrane ↓ (modulate collagen-cell interactions) Regulate integrins, matrix remodeling, adhesion	[114-117]	A combination ?

Remodeling in ECM	Elastin – Fibrillins (fibrillin-2) <i>FBN2</i> , (membrane- anchored) metallo- proteinase (<i>MT- MMP</i>)	Extracellular elastin ↓ (organization by fibrillin-2 , MT-MMP degradation of elastin ↓ (inhibited by TIMP-1/2) Elastin Remodeling ← (influenced by) Dlx5/Hand1	[224, 230]	A combination ?
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431 *FGF: Fibroblast Growth Factor, EGFR: Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor, TGF-β: transforming growth factor beta, PDGF-Rβ: Platelet-
432 Derived Growth Factor Receptor Beta, PDGF-C: Platelet-Derived Growth Factor C, IGF1/2: Insulin-like Growth Factor 1 and 2, TK: tyrosine
433 kinase, HIF-1: hypoxia-induced factor, FAK: Focal Adhesion Kinase, tfs: Transcription factors, SMO: Smoothened, PAI-1: plasminogen activator
434 inhibitor-1, TF: Tissue Factor, MPF: megakaryocyte potentiating factor, coded by the *MSLN* gene, SrcK: SRC proto-oncogene, non-receptor
435 tyrosine kinase, MAPK: Mitogen-activated protein kinase, ERK: extracellular signal-regulated kinases, PI3Ks: Phosphoinositide 3-kinases, AKT:
436 Protein kinase B, PTEN: Phosphatase and tensin homolog, VEGFA/VEGFR: vascular endothelial growth factor (receptor), NOS: Nitric oxide
437 synthase, GPX4&FSP1: glutathione peroxidase 4/ ferroptosis suppressor 1, CDKN2A: cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A, WASP/N-WASP:
438 (neural) Wiskott-Aldrich Syndrome protein, Scar: WAVE regulatory complex, PDLIM3: Actin-associated LIM protein, NF-κB: nuclear factor
439 'kappa-light-chain-enhancer' of activated B-cells, ZF: zinc finger, bHLH: Basic helix–loop–helix, CA125: Mucin-16, GLI: Zinc finger protein,
440 PTCH: Patched-1 receptor, METTL3: N6-adenosine-methyltransferase, SHH: Hedgehog, GPCR: G protein-coupled receptors, FOXO: forkhead
441 box transcription factors, p53: p53 tumor suppressor protein, WNT: Wingless Int-1 signaling pathway, HOOK2: Protein Hook homolog 2,
442 MYC: regulator & proto-oncogenes for tfs, ASCL: Achaete-scute homolog 1, KLF11: Krueppel-like factor 11, RARB: Retinoic acid receptor beta,
443 RAREs: RA response elements, BAP1: ubiquitin carboxy-terminal hydrolase, SWI/SNF: SWItch/Sucrose Non-Fermentable chromatin
444 remodeling complexes), PRRs: Pattern recognition receptors, AMPs: antimicrobial peptides, IgG&IgM&IgA: antibodies, CLEC: C-type lectins,
445 MBL: Mannose-binding lectin CD209: fungal DC-SIGN C-type lectin, CRP: inflammatory opsonin C-reactive protein, IL-6R: nterleukin-6
446 Receptor, JAK/STAT: Janus kinase (JAK) /Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription, MXRA5 & GLT25D2: Matrix Remodeling Associated
447 5 and Glycosyltransferase 25 Domain Containing 2 proteins, DDR1/2: Discoidin domain receptors 1 and 2, CSF1: Macrophage Colony-
448 Stimulating Factor, BMP2: Bone Morphogenetic Protein 2, GDF-15: Growth Differentiation Factor 15, Dlx5: Distal-less homeobox 5 tf, Hand1:
449 Heart and neural crest derivatives expressed 1 tf. KMN: Network Kn1, Mis12, Ndc80, TSG: tumor suppressor gene, MAPs: Microtubule-
450 Associated Proteins, integrins: transmembrane receptors (e.g. α1β1, α2β1, α11β1), tetraspanin: transmembrane proteins (e.g. CD9, CD81,
451 CD63, GLT25D2)

452 3. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

453 The body's autoregulatory systems are robust, but not infallible — particularly when
454 confronted with non-biodegradable materials like asbestos. While the body attempts to encapsulate
455 or sequester asbestos fibers (e.g., through forming asbestos bodies), these responses are often
456 inadequate to neutralize its long-term impact. This may be because high asbestos exposure is relatively
457 new in human evolutionary terms, and it has not been a selective pressure. Therefore, its persistent
458 fibrous nature and inorganic composition fall outside the range of threats our immune and repair
459 systems evolved to manage effectively [281].

460 Instead, the body treats asbestos as if it were a fiber of either its own origin or a possible
461 pathogen. Asbestos 'tricks' the body into 'thinking' it is responding to a persistent injury or foreign
462 invader. As such, the body uses metabolic machinery available: chronic inflammation ROS,
463 phagocytosis, enzymes and fibrosis. All these machineries are interlinked, but are ineffective because
464 asbestos interferes with all of them, because it resembles key bio-macromolecular fibers with
465 regulatory function. As the body cannot clear the asbestos, the body 'mistakes' its own *modus*
466 *operandi* on a chronic scale. Thus, the remediation, rebalancing and compensatory mechanisms the
467 body utilizes are on a chronic scale also. As the body continuously strives for balance (homeostasis),
468 the compensatory mechanisms are, in fact, damaging.

469 Mutations in MM, and all cancer types for that matter, are not random. Mutations cause genes
470 to be non-functioning, therefore, the body may overexpress the gene to try offsetting its low
471 effectivity. Specific genes are over-expressed because they are used to compensate and remediate the
472 disbalance caused by asbestos mimicking biofibers. Those parts of DNA that are overexpressed (e.g.
473 demethylated) i.e., 'opened up', are more susceptible and vulnerable for adverse alterations and
474 mutation. Upon aging, eventually, everyone would get MM unless struck by a different fatality. Cancer
475 involves an increased metabolic age (e.g. methylation patterns), over the 'actual' physiological age
476 [282]. The continued openness and 'attack' is what speeds up metabolic aging. Asbestos speeds up
477 metabolic aging, as the amount of rebalancing needed accumulates over time.

478 While direct evidence for fiber mimicry as a pathomechanism remains limited, experimental
479 and clinical observations support individual aspects of the hypothesis which reflects the need for a
480 unifying framework to bridge those gaps and conceptually integrate the fragments into a coherent
481 mechanistic model that can guide future testing. On future research targeting progression of MM, I
482 can state: if asbestos didn't mimic biological fibers, the body may recognize and eliminate it more
483 effectively. Therefore, future research could focus on 1) further elucidation of which biological
484 structures asbestos mimics exactly, to allow for development of targeted therapies that disrupt the
485 mimicry, 2) developing agents to prime the immune system to target the mimicry by asbestos, so that
486 it may recognize the subtly different features of asbestos and remove them, and 3) developing drugs
487 to target the chronic pathways triggered by the mimicry to mitigate the long-term damage.

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493 ETHICS STATEMENT

494 This study did not involve human participants, animal experiments, or the use of identifiable
495 personal data, and therefore did not require ethical approval.

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499 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION DECLARATION

500 Dr. Nolte: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft,
501 Visualization

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